

ANTHROPONYMS IN DIFFERENT FORMS OF ADDRESS IN ENGLISH AND GERMAN

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ANNOTATION

In English and German, personal names (variants and derivatives of names) and surnames can be used as addresses. In everyday communication between family members, the most common forms of the abbreviated name (English John, Cary, German Ann, Tob), their variants formed using suffixes (English Jonny , Carie , German Anchen , Tobi). English and German languages have an expressive way of word formation of anthroponyms, i.e. suffixes can have their own emotional and/or evaluative meaning, characterizing not only the bearer of the name, but also the name giver . Compared to the German language, the English language has a significantly smaller set of word-forming suffixes. This conclusion is confirmed by the words of M. Epstein: "English, by simplifying, reduced the word to a nominative and informative root, to an informative unit, free from expressive layers." Let's consider the basic rules for using personal names in the field of interpersonal communication. Communication in English and German is impossible to imagine without the use of surnames and personal names. The second and third names are used very rarely in spoken language. The full form of the anthroponymic formula is used only in documents, certificates, official papers, etc.

Key words: derivatives of names; anthroponym; proper name; translation; transcription; transliteration; tracing paper;

The official form of addressing a person is the surname combined with the words Mr , Mrs and Miss - in English, Herr , Frau - in German: addressing a man: English. Mr + last name (surname), German. Herr + surname (Name), for example: English. Mr Smith , Mr Jones , German Herr Ackermann , Herr Forst ; address to a married woman: English. Mrs + husband's last name, German. Frau + husband's surname, for example: English. Mrs Taylor , Mrs Collins , German Frau Dittmar , Frau Hass . address to an unmarried woman: English. Miss + maiden name, German. jungle Frau + maiden name, or just last name, for example: English. Miss Brown , Miss Harvey , German jungle Frau Holzer , junge Frau Jäger . addressing a woman if her situation unknown: English Ms + woman's last name, e.g. Ms Davis , Ms. Gilbert . This form of address has not been found in the German language. Thus, we can conclude that in German the forms Herr and Frau are parallel to the forms Mr and Mrs in English. The presence of gaps in addressing an unmarried woman and addressing a woman if her position is unknown in German, compared to English, can be explained by the fact that in German-speaking in the sociocultural community, a woman's marital status is not as important as for an English speaker sociocultural community. A woman is considered on an equal basis with a man, which is quite natural, since in German-speaking countries the tendencies of feminism in society are more developed and widespread than in English-speaking countries. The presence of only one form of address to men in English. Mr + last name (surname), German. Herr + surname (

Name), it seems possible to explain by the fact that for society the marital status of men is not important, unlike women (in English), which may be the result of many years of patriarchal structure in these two linguistic communities . More recently, the form Mx + surname has appeared in English , which is used in parallel with the forms Mr / Ms + surname. The Mx form is a gender neutral form and due to the tendency to neutralize gender differences between men and women in society, this form is now becoming very popular in formal communication, for example: Mx Thomas , Mx Robinson . In 2013, in the county of Sussex in England, this form of address began to be used in official documents, in 2014 in Scotland. In 2015, Form Mx was approved by Members of the British Parliament and began to be officially used throughout the United Kingdom and beyond in government agencies, passport offices, banks, public and charitable organizations, healthcare institutions, universities, and insurance companies. Also, in 2015, the Mx form was added to Oxford English Dictionary , in 2016 in Merriam-Webster Unabridged Dictionary . An interesting fact is that, on the one hand, more forms of addressing women were discovered in English, these forms are more diverse and subtly differentiate the status of women in society, on the other hand, only in English was a gender-neutral form of address discovered, which can be used when addressing both women and men, which indicates equal treatment in society to representatives of both sexes. Therefore, English speaking The linguistic community represents the intersection point of both the centuries-old traditions of the patriarchal community and the advanced trends of the modern world of globalization. In some cases in English, official address is carried out using the words Sir and Madam , but in German there is no equivalent to these lexemes: I am sorry , sir !, will you help me , madam ? In English and German, sometimes the address is simply by last name (without Mrs , Mr , Miss , Ms in English and Herr , Frau in German). The words Mr , Mrs , Miss in English and Herr , Frau in German are always combined with the surname in polite address and business situations. But this is the language of official communication. This is how people address each other at work or at school (students to teachers). In everyday life, these forms are rarely used.

Neutral forms of addressing a person. The forms of address Mr , Mrs , Miss in English Herr , Frau - in German + surname are used not only in cases of official address, but also at the level of neutral communication between people of respectable age, even in cases where they have known each other for a very long time: English Mrs Cook, Mr White, Miss Clarke, German . Herr Kahler , Frau Maier. The surname as an independent form of address functions in a strictly limited number of situations in English and German . Just by last name (English Harris , Green , Patel ; German Luther , Mann , Achterberg) can be addressed by: owners to doormen, footmen, maids, etc. (official form of address); teachers and teachers to students (official form of address); officers to soldiers (official form of address); clients to well-known ordinary service workers - salespeople, cashiers, tailors, etc. (neutral form of address); Frequent visitors to bars and restaurants see familiar waiters (neutral form of address). An interesting case is the use of the surname as an address in German, which was not found in English, in situations where the wife expresses an equal relationship with her husband: Schmidt , komm nothing zu spat ! 'Schmidt, come not too late!' People who hold certain positions are addressed using a title or a combination of title and surname, for example: Doctor ! / Doctor ! Professor !, Captain! Hauptmann! English _ Professor White!, Doctor Gray !, Captain Blackwood! German _ Professor Bach!, Doktor Goldschmidt !, Hauptmann Jundt ! First present the one whose title higher .

Familiar forms of addressing a person. People you know are usually addressed using just their personal name. Personal names have short forms that are used much more often than full forms in oral communication: Emily > Em , Gilbert > Gill , Robert > Rob , Bob , Albert > Bert , Christopher > Chris , Elizabeth > Liz , Beth , Alexander > Alex , German . Michael> Mike, Daniel> Dan, Helena> Lena, Vanessa> Nessa , Samuel> Sam. English and German personal names often have affectionate forms, for example: English. William – Willy (Billy), Elizabeth – Libby German _ Daniel > Dani , Anna > Anja , Thomas > Tomke , etc. Parents can address their children, children, friends, and youth can address each other using only their first name. In the family in the English and German linguistic communities, they address parents using the term kinship, children - by name, relatives - by name, or use the term kinship and name: aunt Agatha , uncle James , German Tante Emma , Onkel Paul _ An elderly person can address a young person using only a personal name, and a boss can also address a subordinate with whom he has good friendly relations. It is necessary to be extremely careful when communicating with German and English speakers when moving to a familiar level of communication, because... Replacing a polite or neutral form of address with a familiar one is equivalent to switching from “You” to “You” with Russian-speaking people. So, in the English-speaking and German-speaking linguistic communities, communication between people occurs according to three politeness systems - official, neutral and familiar. Each politeness system has its own rules, style, and the use of personal names is subject to certain rules.

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